

SELECTION OF PRINCIPLES FOR THE REPAIR, PROTECTION, AND STRENGTHENING OF HIGH-STRENGTH FLOOR STRUCTURES

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The need for repair or strengthening of high-strength floors is recommended to be determined on the basis of data obtained during inspections in accordance with DSTU-N B V.1.2-18, DSTU B V.3.1-2, and the results of verification calculations performed according to DBN V.2.6-98 and DSTU B V.2.6-156.

The principles of repair, protection, and strengthening of high-strength floor structures include: repair, protection, and strengthening in cases of concrete damage caused by various factors (mechanical, physico-chemical, operational, etc.); and repair, protection, and strengthening in cases of damage to concrete and reinforcement caused by corrosion.

The choice of repair, protection, and strengthening principles should be made according to the defects and damages revealed during inspection, their causes or combinations of causes, the extent of damage and the rate of its progression, assessment of the condition of the high-strength floor structure, and calculation of the residual service life of the building, in accordance with DBN V.1.2-14.

A detailed inspection of the structure, aimed at identifying and clarifying the extent of defects and damages, identifying or clarifying their causes, as well as choosing the principles and methods of repair, includes: classification of existing defects and damages; determination of the types and magnitudes of the loads applied; assessment of the aggressiveness of the operating environment on the reinforced concrete structure, taking into account the type of environment and the nature of the impact; identification of causes of defects and damages based on analysis of the results obtained; and carrying out special studies, if necessary, to clarify the results.

The assessment of the technical condition of the structure and the selection of evaluation criteria is performed in the following sequence: load-bearing capacity (Ultimate Limit State, ULS, of the first group); serviceability for normal operation (Serviceability Limit State, SLS, of the second group).

The assessment and calculation of the residual service life of the structure until failure is carried out according to one of the selected criteria, using various methods, including mathematical modeling.

The choice and adaptation of the repair, protection, and strengthening principles for high-strength floors are performed taking into account the operating conditions after the repair is completed.

The design of strengthening or repair of concrete and reinforced concrete structures is carried out on the basis of inspection data, which include: data on the strength characteristics of concrete; data on the

strength characteristics of reinforcing steel; and the results of verification calculations performed with consideration of identified defects and damages.

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